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CHALLENGES AND FUTURE OF OUTSOURCING INDUSTRY IN INDIA.

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Abstract

Outsourcing is one of the fastest growing industry on the world platform. It mainly involves transfer of components or large segments of the companies' internal production processes, businesses, or infrastructure, etc. to the external service operators or providers. It can cover a wide range of components and activities depending upon the core competency and the requirements of the outsourcing firm. It may be broadly classified into information technology (IT), human resource, customer service, engineering, knowledge services, legal, Research and Development outsourcing, etc.

India has emerged as the 21st century's software powerhouse, offering many advantages as a global sourcing hub, especially for IT enabled Services (ITES) and Business Process Outsourcing (BPO), Owing to its advantageous factors like presence of one of the world-best intellectual and internet resources, lower cost structure, multi-lingual capabilities, etc. The main motive behind outsourcing has been that it allows a company to invest more time, money and human resources in core active items without losing quality and name and that's why Call centres have also mushroomed in India serving various foreign airlines and banks.

Introduction:

Information Technology (IT) has made possible information access at gigabit speeds. It has created a level playing field among nations has created a positive impact on the lives of millions.

Today, a country's IT potential is paramount for its march towards global competitiveness, healthy gross domestic product (GDP) and therefore The Indian IT and Information Technology enabled Services (Ites)

sectors go hand-in-hand in every aspect meeting up the requirements of outsourcing firm as well as energy and environmental challenges.

The industry has not only transformed India's image on the global platform, but also fuelled economic growth by the industry that has employed almost 10 million Indians and, hence, has contributed significantly to social transformation in the country energising the higher education sector (especially in engineering and computer science), also known throughout the world as largest outsourcing destination, accounting for approximately 52 per cent of the US\$ 124–130 billion market. India is one of the fastest-growing IT services markets in the world because of cost competitiveness and its effectiveness in providing IT services continues to be its USP in the global sourcing market. India has the potential to build a US\$ 100 billion software product industry by 2025, according to Indian Software Product Industry Round table (ISPIRT). The software products market in India, which includes accounting software and cloud computing-based telephony services, is expected to grow at 14 per cent in 2014. .

Further, economic success of the BPO industry has taken many firms to their advanced knowledge work to off shore destinations. Knowledge Processing Outsourcing (KPO) is one step extension of BPO and can be defined as high added value processes chain where the achievement of objectives is highly dependent on the skills, domain knowledge and experience of the people carrying out the activity. The KPO typically involves a component of BPO, Research Process Outsourcing (RPO) and Analysis Process Outsourcing (APO). The Department of Electronics and Information Technology is coordinating strategic activities, promoting skill development programmes, enhancing infrastructure capabilities and supporting research and development (R&D) for India's leadership position in IT and ITES among western countries as United States (US) and United Kingdom (UK) are the key markets for Indian IT-KPO exports. As a result, India continues to dominate global outsourcing market with market size estimated to be worth about \$52 billion. Banking and financial services contribute nearly 40 percent to India's outsourcing industry.

At the Central level, the Department of Electronics and Information Technology, under the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology, which is the main authority responsible for the overall development of outsourcing business in India. Accordingly, separate Departments of Information Technology have been set up in all the States/ Union Territories. Both Central and State Governments as well as private sector/ MNCs have been making continuous efforts and lending a helping hand to develop this industry on a sustainable basis. But still requirement is to develop the adequate talent base, providing technical knowledge and design appropriate training programmes for all BPO employees, incorporate proper and adequate health care policies as well as implement safety measures, especially for Indian women. But, then also outsourcing industry has been facing many challenges, like, cut-throat competition, severe shortages of trained and skilled manpower, more investment needed in KPO infrastructure, need of higher level of control, maintenance of higher quality standards, etc. Besides, there are several problems faced by BPO employees which affects their health and lifestyle, namely, working in night shifts, problem of sexual harassment at workplace, etc. In case of offshore outsourcing, cultural mismatch or language barriers can pose a big risk.

As of 2012, around 2.8 million people work in outsourcing sector.^[1] Annual revenues are around \$11 billion,^[1] around 1% of GDP. Around 2.5 million people graduate in India every year. Wages are rising by 10-15 percent as a result of skill shortage.^[1] "India's outsourcing revenue to hit \$50 bn...financial express,2008

(<http://www.financialexpress.com/news/indias-outsourcing-revenue-to-hit-50-bn/266661>)

Several measures and initiatives are being undertaken by both the Central and State Governments, with a view to establish strong and stable outsourcing industry in India. Besides, many big corporates are also making all efforts to push upward this industry and have been tremendous efforts, Owing to advantages that India has with respect to the growth of this industry, many policies and schemes have been launched from time to time. accordingly, conducting surveys and studies to acknowledge the current and future scenario of outsourcing in India.

At the Central level, the nodal agency responsible for the overall development of outsourcing and information technology (IT) industry has been the Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Ministry of Communications and Information Technology. It is mainly responsible for formulation, implementation and review of national policies in the field of IT and ITeS, the Department aims to make India a global IT super power and a front-runner in the age of information revolution. All policy matters relating to silicon facility, computer based information technology and processing including hardware and software, standardization of procedures and matters relating to international bodies, promotion of knowledge based enterprises, Internet, e-Commerce and information technology education and development of electronics and coordination are some of its various functional areas.

At the State/ Union Territory level, there are several organisations dealing with the matters relating to IT and BPO sectors. Some of these are:-

- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Delhi
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Kerala (most noticeable, Kerala State IT Mission)
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Punjab
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, West Bengal
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Karnataka
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Chandigarh
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Himachal Pradesh
- Secretariat of Information Technology, Haryana
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Meghalaya
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Odisha
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Nagaland
- Department of Electronics and Information Technology, Jammu & Kashmir, etc.

Opportunities

Information technology enabled services (ITES) and BPO are the fastest growing sectors in the Indian IT industry, both in terms of employment opportunities and revenue generation, Outsourcing industry is the sunrise industry in India, which plays a vital role in the sustained growth of the economy. It is, roughly, growing at the rate of 60-70 per cent per annum. This industry is estimated to be worth about \$52 billion. Its main driving forces being the Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) and Knowledge Process Outsourcing (KPO).

This is due to the advantageous position of India in having one of the largest pools of low cost, English speaking, scientific and technical talent, The Indians have become a highly sought after career option for fresh graduates, especially those from the Information Technology (IT) sector. The total number of IT and ITES-BPO professionals employed in India have grown from 2,84,000 in 1999-2000 to over 1.63 million in 2006-07. The direct employment by this industry has grown at a compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) of 26 per cent in the last decade, making it the largest employer in the organized private sector of the country.

A company can set up its own call centre to deal with its customers, and/ or it can hire a professional firm to do the job as there are numerous opportunities in setting up and development of both domestic and international call centres in India On one hand, these creates more employment opportunities for people at large with good pay package, and on other hand, brings global businesses into the country and thus, helps to increase India's national income. Hence, as the outsourcing activities booming in the world, India stands to gain with more foreign exchange earnings.

Further, BPO exports from India grew from US\$ 3.1 billion in year 2003-04 to over US\$ 8.4 billion in the year 2006-07. The Indian software and services exports including ITES-BPO are estimated at US\$ 40.3 billion (Rs. 163,000 crores) in 2007-08, as compared to US\$ 31.4 billion (Rs. 141,000 crore) in fiscal year 2006-07, an increase of 28.3 per cent in dollar terms and 15.6 per cent in rupee terms. Further, the export revenues from ITES-BPO are estimated to grow from US\$ 8.4 billion (Rs. 37,700 crores) in year 2006-07 to US\$ 10.9 billion (Rs. 44,600 crore) in year 2007-08, a year-on-year growth of over 30 per cent (in dollar terms) and 18.3 per cent (in rupee terms)

Here, major advantages and opportunity areas for India is cost savings, operational efficiencies, access to the skilled and talented workforce, multilingual capabilities and improved quality norms, therefore KPO sector is increasingly becoming most preferred option for the growth of Indian economy, where the Indian companies outsource their high-end knowledge work. Thus, it is a great opportunity for India to acquire major chunk of income from such countries Further, business of India's outsourcing industry mainly comes from advanced and developed countries like United States (US), United Kingdom (UK), etc as these are the key markets for Indian IT-BPO exports (excluding hardware), accounting for nearly 80 per cent of the total exports, Also, this encourages Indian counterparts to upgrade the skills of their present employees, improve working conditions, improve quality standards, etc. Although the industry is steadily

increasing its exposure to other markets like Continental Europe and Asia Pacific. This is a positive opportunity for Indian outsourcing industry, but it is creating many innovative business models that can actually save precious management time and resources as well as allow companies to focus on their core competencies, in spite India's outsourcing business has been facing many challenges, internally as well as from global markets, In order to meet international standards, outsourcing to India is now focussing more on high and stable quality systems rather than only on cost savings.

It has led not only to job creation and income generation, but also triggered the growth process of several ancillary industries such as transportation, real estate and catering, etc. as well as created a rising class of young consumers with high disposable incomes, triggered a rise in direct-tax collections and propelled an increase in consumer spending a noticeable sign by IT-BPO sector which is export driven, the domestic market is also significant. BPO demand in the domestic market has witnessed noticeable growth over the past few years

There exists innumerable opportunities in Indian outsourcing industry and is considered to be an attractive and profitable destinations for investors worldwide. All these shows that India is poised to emerge as a global powerhouse for outsourcing of IT software, ITES and BPO/ KPO sectors and for other types of outsourcing categories as well also the industry has also helped in increasing adoption of technology which enhances performance and competitiveness in the domestic market as well as seeks to reduce economic disparities by greater participation of women in the workforce.

Market Size¹³

Indian IT and ITES industry is divided into four major segments – IT services, business process management (BPM), software products and engineering services, and hardware. With a huge market size, India's outsourcing is still continuing to dominate the global outsourcing market. Though there are many competitors in the market like China, Malaysia, Philippines, etc., it is still the major player in the world in outsourcing due to its many advantageous factors. As a proportion of national GDP, the IT-BPO sector revenues have grown from 5.2 per cent in 2006-07 to an estimated 5.5 per cent in 2007-08. On the export front, revenue from ITES-BPO have shown a year-on-year growth of over 29.8 per cent (from 2006-07 to 2007-08). Also, direct employment in Indian BPO grew from 2,16,000 in year 2003-04 to 5,53,000 in year 2006-07. India has already registered its mark on the globe in IT-BPO sector. While, huge opportunities in KPO sector will help the Indian market climb the global value and knowledge chain, the IT services sector accounted for the largest share of the IT and ITeS industry, with a total market size of US\$ 56.3 billion during FY13, followed by BPM sector (US\$ 20.9 billion), and software products and engineering services (US\$ 17.9 billion); the market size for hardware was US\$ 13.3 billion during FY12.

The Indian IT-BPM industry is expected to add revenues of US\$ 13–14 billion to the existing revenues by FY15, according to National Association of Software and Services Companies (NASSCOM).

The industry grew at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 13.1 per cent during FY08–13. Total exports from the IT-BPM sector (excluding hardware) were estimated at US\$ 76 billion during FY13. Export of IT services has been the major contributor, accounting for 57.9 per cent of total IT exports (excluding hardware) in FY13. BPM accounted for 23.5 per cent of total IT exports during the same fiscal. The IT outsourcing sector is expected to see exports growing by 13–15 per cent during FY15.

The technology industry of India will have a US\$ 37 billion of CMO opportunity by 2020, according to a report titled 'Marketing, Disrupted: Opportunities for the Indian technology industry' by NASSCOM and Sapient Nitro.

Outsourcing may be broadly classified into the following types:

- Information Technology (IT);
- Human Resource (HR);
- Customer Service;
- Engineering;
- Knowledge Services;
- R&D; etc..

The future potential of KPO is quite high because it is not restricted to Information Technology (IT) or Information Technology Enabled Services (ITES) sectors and includes other sectors like Legal Processes, Intellectual Property and Patent related services, Engineering Services, Web Development application, Business Research and Analytics, Clinical Research, Market Research, etc.

In today's competitive environment, focus is only to concentrate on core specialization and core-competency areas and outsource the remaining of the activities. Many companies and organizations have come to realize that by outsourcing non core activities, not only cost are minimized and efficiencies improved but the total business which has made their product cost effective and sales improves because the focus shifts to the key growth areas of the business activity.

Advantages and Disadvantages

The main motive behind business process outsourcing is to allow a company to invest more time, money and human resources in core active items without losing quality and name. Thus, cost advantage followed by increased ability to focus on core competencies is the major driving factor. Other advantages for a firm include:

- Improved efficiency and operational performance;
- Productivity improvements;
- Access to expertise and superior competency;
- Operational cost control;

- Improved accountability;
- Shorter project delivery times;
- Opportunity to focus on core business concerns;
- Enhanced employment opportunities;
- Handling of miscellaneous jobs;
- Access to newer markets (in case off shoring);
- benefits derived from the experience of the service provider; etc.

Thus, business process outsourcing assists in increasing a company's profits as well as shareholder value. Software companies are trying new avenues through business process outsourcing to increase their revenues. Outsourcing helps convert a fixed cost structure into a variable one and allows for more flexibility in handling of business related uncertainties.

Some of the major risk factors involved in outsourcing are:

- Service expectation mismatch;
- Lower than anticipated cost savings;
- Intellectual property protection
- ; Higher training costs;
- Monitoring costs;
- Compromising confidentiality;
- Loss of control;
- Data theft;
- Information security;
- Customer dissatisfaction; etc.

In case of offshore outsourcing, cultural mismatch or language barrier can pose a great challenge.

Challenges and Future Prospects

India has become one of the most sought after destination for the companies wanting to outsource their business, knowledge, research, legal and related high-end processes. This not only boosts exports, increases national income and creates greater employment avenues, but also increases tax revenues, caters to the growth of other related industries like infrastructure, catering, etc. The companies involved in outsourcing activities tends to earn huge profits out of this and thus, are in a position to offer their employees the good and competitive pay packages, along with many attractive employee benefits.

The industry is continuing this trend by combining provider and industry-level initiatives as well as by generating greater awareness and facilitating wider adoption of standards and best practices. It is moving to provide high-value services to its clients rather than just minimizing/ saving costs, the success of off-

shoring BPO sector in India has led to the emergence of Knowledge Process Outsourcing (KPO) sector in India, which deals with off-shoring of knowledge intensive business processes requiring specialized domain-based expertise, India has already made remarkable achievements in the field of Business Process Outsourcing (BPO), with high export revenues. The Indian IT-BPO sector has been able to build a strong reputation for its high standards of service quality and information security, which has been acknowledged worldwide and also helped to enhance buyer's confidence. The advantage, along with multi-lingual capabilities and advantages of lower costs, can help the country to emerge as a front-runner in KPO on the global platform. India is well endowed with large pool of skilled manpower, like, chartered accountants, doctors, MBAs, lawyers, research analysts, etc., which would help to add value to the global KPO business and its high-end processes like valuation research, investment research, patent filing, legal and insurance claims processing, online teaching, media content supply, etc. But, to be able to run stable outsourcing company (mainly BPO), one needs to overcome the challenges coming in its way. Some of these include: outsourcing is largely fragmented industry; there is more preference for young employees with good command over English and other foreign languages; facing cut-throat competition therefore as per Nasscom estimates, the KPO industry is expected to grow by 45 per cent by 2010. Out of the \$16 billion which the KPO industry is likely to assume by 2010, around \$12 billion would be outsourced from India.

Besides, there are several problems faced by BPO employees which not only affects their health and lifestyle, but also leads to decline in total output of the firm. Some of the prominent ones are:-

- Working in night shifts as clients are mainly US and UK based and there are differences in geographical and time zones of India and abroad. Thus, in order to meet cut-throat competition, the BPO employees have to work in night shifts. But, due to lack of normal sleep, their physical and mental health gets affected in the long run.
- Problem of sexual harassment at workplace, which leads to stress.
- Some of them gets addicted to drugs and/ or gets serious diseases, etc.

Investments by Indian companies.¹³

Indian IT's core competencies and strengths have placed it on the international canvas, attracting investments from major countries.

According to data released by the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP), the computer software and hardware sector attracted foreign direct investment (FDI) worth Rs 59,381.64 crore (US\$ 9.89 billion) between April 2000 and February 2014.

Some of the major investments in Indian IT and ITES sector are as follows:

- Tata Consultancy Services (TCS) plans to merge its two units in Japan with Mitsubishi Corp's IT subsidiary to create a joint venture (JV) company with a revenue base of US\$ 600 million in the world's second-largest market for software services.
- Private equity (PE) firm TPG Growth and India's Smile Group will jointly invest US\$ 100 million to help internet and e-commerce companies build and scale their businesses across the Asia-Pacific region and West Asia.
- Synecron plans to invest US\$ 30–35 million on the expansion of its Hyderabad and Bengaluru facilities.
- Bharti Airtel, India's largest telecom operator, has renewed its technology outsourcing contract with software major IBM for a period of five years.
- Infosys has partnered with telecom company Orange to provide Internet TV to its customers. Infosys will deliver a portfolio of interactive TV apps on the Orange Livebox Play. The TV apps will be powered by Infosys Digitize Edge, a digital asset and experience platform for TV operators, media companies, advertisers and content publishers.

Current trends:

Business process outsourcing (BPO) is a broad term referring to outsourcing in all fields. Indian BPO industry includes basic data and market research, equity research, management, engineering design, animation and simulation, medical content & services and education and publishing. It is the evolution and maturity of the Indian BPO sector that has given rise to yet another wave in the global outsourcing scenario of Knowledge Process Outsourcing (KPO), A BPO differentiates itself by either putting in new technology or applying existing technology in a new way to improve a process. BPO is one of the fastest growing segments of the Information Technology Enabled Services (ITES) industry. In other words, success achieved by many overseas companies in outsourcing business process operations to India has encouraged them to start outsourcing their high-end knowledge work as well. India as a major KPO player in the world has inherent advantages because of its intellectual and internet resource.

Outsourcing to India give organizations a competitive edge in the form of:

- Cost-effective services without compromising on quality due to a large pool of educated, trained and highly-skilled professionals;
- High-quality services due to use of the latest in software, technology and infrastructure;
- Time Zone advantage between India and countries in the U.S and U.K, helps companies provide 24x7x365 days customer support or helpdesk services;
- Democratic set up and stable Government which has been giving complete support for expansion of the IT and ITES industry in India; etc.

Effects on Indian Economy

Software and BPO industry in India has provided a major boost to the country's economy, In 2008, a study listed 6 Indian cities of Bangalore, Chennai, Delhi-NCR, Hyderabad, Mumbai, and Pune, among the world's top 10 outsourcing destinations.

It provides employment to millions of Indians. BPO industry in India is worth \$11 billion. During 2007-08, Indian information technology industry experienced a slow down and revenue growth rate has been brought down to 21 percent from previous year figure of 41 percent. But it's still predicted that Indian BPO and IT industry will grow to become a \$132 billion entity by 2012. Banking and financial services contribute nearly 40 percent to India's outsourcing industry.

Nevertheless, the big boom in the BPO industry in India has generated a lot of employment opportunities with lots of benefits to their employees. Some of which are in the form of:

- Provident Fund;
- Gratuity;
- Group Mediclaim Insurance Scheme;
- Personal Accident Insurance Scheme;
- Subsidized Food and Transportation;
- Company Leased Accommodation;
- Recreation, Cafeteria, ATM and Concierge facilities;
- Corporate Credit Card;
- Cellular Phone / Laptop;
- Personal Health Care (Regular medical check-ups);
- Educational Benefits;
- Performance based incentives;
- Flexi-time;
- Flexible Salary Benefits;
- Maternity Leave;
- Employee Stock Option Plan; etc.

Generally, growth of BPO industry is largely influenced by the existing location factors of a country. It includes size of workforce, wage differentials, stable and conducive business environment, telecom infrastructure, trade restrictions and above all the language capabilities. India can boast of all these attributes barring few deterrents.

Suggestions and Opinions

Since its evolution, India's outsourcing industry has been facing many challenges and restrictions, which affects the growth of BPO companies and their employees. In order to meet international quality standards, the Indian BPO industry should be providing consistency along with customer satisfaction, as it cannot take

full benefits of the potentials only with advantages like lower costs and multi-lingual capabilities. Further, it can add value to its customers by proactively acquiring domain knowledge of its client's business. Thus, the need of the hour is to take some useful steps for sound and healthy development of BPOs/ KPOs in India. Several steps have been taken by the Government, both at the Central and State level, towards better management of outsourcing activities in economy and to keep India's position stable as hub of outsourcing on the global platform. Given this, some of the suggestions can be listed as follows:

- Develop the talent base by generating/ encouraging enough opportunities for technical knowledge.
- Design appropriate training programmes for BPO employees.
- Provide broad and essential hands-on experience.
- Improve choices and processes used by companies and make outsourcing easier by getting more and more organisations moving to the outsourced model.
- Follow proper code of ethics and procedures in recruitment of employees.
- Ensure proper control and quality management systems.
- Enactment of appropriate social security laws.
- Incorporate best practices on health and safety hazards.
- Develop sound work environment with proper safety of women at workplace.

Follow better healthcare policy which involves regular health-checkup of employees and this feature should be made compulsory.

Develop time management and other strategies so as to encourage healthy lifestyle habits of BPO employees, like, having proper sleep, preventing fatigue and stress, etc.

Moreover, along with customer care and support services, other service lines should also be considered in broad manner, such as, of finance, human resource, legal procedure, content development, etc. Most importantly, there should be joint efforts by both public and private sectors to keep sustainable India's advantages in outsourcing industry and explore all untapped areas. Increased innovation and technology adoption should be the guiding force.

Table 1: Global Indian BPO Market by Industry^[3]

Industry	Percentage (%)
Information Technology	43
Financial Services	17
Communication (Telecom)	16
Consumer Goods/ Services	15
Manufacturing	9

Size and Growth of BPO in India^[3]

Year	Size (US\$ Bn)	Growth Rate (%)
2003	2.8	59
2004	3.9	45.3
2005	5.7	44.4

Call Centre Employee cost^[3]

Country	Cost (USD/yr)
United States	19,000
Australia	17,000
India	<7,500

("The Evolution of BPO in India" (PDF). Price WaterHouse Coopers April 2005)

Government spending accounts for about one-third of the overall spending in the domestic IT market, which industry body Nasscom expects to grow 9-12% during fiscal 2014-15. While most Indian software providers operate at a 20% profit margin in large markets such as the United States and Europe, they say profit margins in India fall in the single digits due to late payments and delays. In fiscal year 2013-14, the government spent close to Rs 20,000-crore on IT, according to Nasscom.

(http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2014-05-15/news/49873632_1_government-contracts-government-spending-hcl-technologies)

Road Ahead¹³

The Government of India played a key role with public funding of a large, well trained pool of engineers and management personnel who could forge the Indian IT industry.

The Central Government and the respective State Governments are expected to collectively spend US\$ 6.4 billion on IT products and services in 2014, an increase of 4.3 per cent over 2013, according to a study by Gartner.

Some of the major initiatives taken by the Government to promote IT and ITeS sector in India are as follows:

- The Government of Bihar has unveiled 20 km free Wi-Fi zone in Patna, the longest across the planet, making a strong impression on the world's infotech map.
- The Government of India has given an in-principle approval for setting up of the first electronic system design and manufacturing (ESDM) cluster development in Electronics City, Bengaluru. The ESDM project will come up on a 1.16 acre of land at an investment of approximately Rs 85 crore (US\$ 14.16 million).

- More than 20 small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the IT sector have recently received land allotment letters from the Government of Punjab to set up their units with an investment of Rs 500 crore (US\$ 83.24 million).
- The Government of India planned and announce a national policy on cloud computing, as per Mr Kapil Sibal, Minister of Communications and Information Technology.
- The Governments of Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu are in talks with NASSCOM to set up 'start-up warehouses' for incubation of start-ups. The centres are expected to come up in Mumbai and Chennai and are likely to be operational by December 2014.

India is the most preferred location for engineering offshoring, according to a customer poll conducted by Booz and Co. Companies are now off shoring complete product responsibility. Increased focus on R&D by IT firms in India has resulted in rising number of patents filed by them.

India's IT sector is gradually moving from linear models (rising headcount to increase revenue) to non-linear ones.

In line with this, IT companies in the country are focusing on new models such as platform-based BPM services and creation of intellectual property.

Tier II and III cities are increasingly gaining traction among IT companies aiming to establish business in India.

Cheap labour, affordable real estate, favourable government regulations, tax breaks and special economic zone (SEZ) schemes are facilitating their emergence as new IT destinations.

Indian insurance companies also plan to spend Rs 12,100 crore (US\$ 2.01 billion) on IT products and services in 2014, a 12 per cent rise over 2013, according to Gartner. This forecast includes spending by insurers on internal IT (including personnel), software, hardware, external IT services and telecommunications.

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